

THE FUNCTION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN A MODERN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: This scientific work proposes the role of learning foreign languages with its beneficial aspects. Learning foreign languages broadens our minds, people become educated. In my opinion, languages are especially important for those who work in different fields of science and technology, in politics. A foreign language helps to know the native language better. People, who know many languages are called polyglots. We know the names of some of them: German professor Shlimman, famous writer Shakespeare, philosopher Socrates and many others.

Initially, foreign languages are absolutely necessary for people nowadays, because of our growing international contacts with foreign countries. It is useful to speak at least one foreign language as with its help we can communicate with people who speak it and this ability is useful in our life. Every year thousands of people go from one country to another either on business or for pleasure. And the knowledge of languages opens the door to any foreign country and gives them a possibility to communicate, to understand people and to be understood.

Keywords: language, English, Japanese ,multiculturalism, polyglots, bilingual, scientific research, interaction, sensibilities, immersion, psycholinguistic, culture, society.

Introduction

As, of May 6, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev chaired a meeting on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, several improvements have been made in this sector. It should be noted that learning foreign languages can benefit both at the individual and governmental levels. Therefore, foreign languages have been prioritized at a governmental scale for the last decade in our country. On this basis, the issue of attitudes to foreign language teaching is addressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021

No PP-5117 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level": "... education in foreign languages. It is no coincidence that the need to develop as a policy priority, radically improve the quality of education in this area, attract qualified teachers to the field and increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages".

There are more than thousands of languages spoken in the entire world but only a few have gained wide prominence over the years, for instance, English, Mandarin, Urdu, Hindi, Japanese, Malayan and etc. The importance of language in our society is clear as it has helped to smooth social contacts, preserve our culture and convey our thoughts to individuals and people in groups effectively.

Actually, language is defined as a formal system that includes sounds, signs, symbols, and gestures that are used as an important means of communicating the thoughts, ideas, and emotions from one individual to another. Its effectual use has been a blessing in forging interpersonal relationships both in personal and professional front.

The usage of language successfully is very important in the global world so that you can make others understand what you want to convey. Remember it is one of the skills that a person is not born with but one that can be easily learned with a little effort and hard work. The importance of language is that it is one of the primary means of interaction and communication. Hence make sure that the language you are using is appropriate for your specific audience and is familiar to him and he can grasp its meaning.

In an age of multiculturalism language plays an important role. It contributes not only for the culture preservation but also in the realization of the different cultural sensibilities. Due to the globalization and increasing mobility of human beings, many languages come together. There is lot of scope for language contact. Many languages come in contact of each other affecting each other. In this context borrowing becomes more adaptable enriching languages. In the process of borrowing the loan word i.e. the word borrowed becomes the established part of the particular language. Along with the word the culture of that language is also accepted to some extent. Thus the multilingualism also leads to multiculturalism. Due to language contact we get more opportunities for code switching and code mixing. With the help of code mixing we can express

our cultural experiences in more effective way. We get new avenues to understand different cultures in most convenient way.

The main findings and results

Language is obviously a vital tool. Not only is it a means of communicating thoughts and ideas, but it forges friendships, cultural ties, and economic relationships. Humans developed some pretty big brains along the way. One leading hypothesis as to why that much brain was necessary to our survival is that we have complex social systems to navigate that are a little more intricate than simply "existing in large groups." The development of language played a pretty big role in that. Specifically, the kind of language that makes it possible to tell stories, negotiate with others, plan for the future and talk about what happened in the past. Other animals also have languages of their own, but their function is largely to communicate about things that are immediately relevant in the present moment.

Throughout history, many have reflected on the importance of language. For instance, the scholar Benjamin Whorf has noted that language shapes thoughts and emotions, determining one's perception of reality. John Stuart Mill said that "Language is the light of the mind."

There are many reasons why we begin to study foreign languages. First of all, it is an effective medium of international communication. I'm convinced if we are working in any brunch of science we must read books and magazines in other languages. Learning foreign languages opens up opportunities and careers that didn't even exits some years ago. Knowing foreign languages can help us to find a job in such fields as science and technology, foreign trade and banking, international transportation communication, teaching librarian science and others. A more general aim is to make our intellectual and cultures. Learning a foreign language including learning also culture, traditions and mode of thought of different people. Of course speaking and writing in a foreign language is a difficult art and it has to be learned.

The research revealed that there are certain stimulators that encourage people to learn the various languages and they are followings:

1. It raises your status in the workplace. Although this is quite obvious, it may not be in the way you think. Knowledge of current language for business will increase your value as a global employer and market player. Whether it's business regarding English or other language, or just

getting your foot through the door with basic greetings, your potential clients, business partners from the world will greatly appreciate your efforts. English business language might lack the conversational tone you are more used to, so more formality is required. It's best to study exactly what is or isn't allowed, and this will save you from committing any faux pas. Learning the basics helps get you started, and it helps you appreciate a foreign culture even more.

2. The language learner will become more approachable. Foreign languages for business shouldn't be your only goal. A little-known fact, for example, unless you have lived in England, you will probably do not speak English so much. Not only that, a large majority of the population is reluctant to speak or use the English they do know. Even if you speak just a little bit of English, a simple —Hello! It will make a noticeable difference. It will prompt English people to be friendlier and more welcoming — after all, you took the trouble to learn something about them instead of expecting them to do all the work.

3. Can further appreciate the culture and entertainment of the foreign country. While we're pretty sure you have tried sushi or ramen in your home country, there's a lot more out there. Learning various languages can help you understand the origins of ingredients, styles of cooking, and even converse with chefs (however basic the conversation maybe).

For instance, when it comes to Japanese language, you may also be familiar with adorable animated characters such as Totoro and Hello Kitty. For English learners: Pitter Pan and Spunch Bob. But do you know the thought and stories that go behind the creation of these beloved cartoons? Likewise, most of cartoons and anime has taken over the entertainment world by storm. And take one of the most vaguely familiar aspects of Japanese culture: Sumo. Sumo wrestling is a sacred sport that originated during the Edo period. It's extremely unique, and the reason for the sport may not be known to many. Sumo is actually a religious ritual, and to be a pro-sumo wrestler is a difficult task. Wrestlers live with many limitations but are very well respected. Knowing more about entertainment and what's trending in Japan could open up opportunities for conversation with your Japanese clients or business partners, and this can be important in relationship-focused business cultures like Japan.

4. It's a self-imposed challenge. In the workplace, many managers and supervisors give raises and promotions based on the work they produce. Many admire a person that challenges

themselves with personal growth. 5. It opens up more doors and job opportunities. For example, English, Russian and Japanese have their way of life, different laws, and a unique way of doing things. This makes certain integration more difficult for some foreigners. Additionally, conducted deeper studies showed that the following reasons can be additional reasons for learning foreign languages:

a) Learning foreign languages grows the brain. Research, how old is the person's age demonstrate the cognitive benefits of learning another language, regardless of the occupation of the person. These studies have shown that the brains of bilingual people are larger, good memory, are creative, have problem-solving, etc. These advantages not only make it easier to learn more languages but to learn everything.

The ability to quickly switch tasks is in today's busy multi-tasking world especially important. Bilingual tasks are much faster than their monolingual counterparts can be exchanged and perform many other tasks at the same time.

b) When an individual learns a foreign language, travel becomes cheaper and easier. Of course, a lot of people love to travel. Knowing the language is up to the person and when they go abroad it gives great benefits. Simply go for a meal and eat whatever you want you can easily explain. Ask for directions from the locals around you and you can find it without difficulties. If you take a guide, it would be costly.

c) Learning a foreign language opens the world to finding work. It is no secret that learning a foreign language can improve employment prospects. More than ever, companies are few, often dozens, in the world are working in their home countries, but they speak at least one foreign language they can't do without hiring people who understand. The ability to speak a second language in local companies also makes you a different business is more likely to be separated from recipients.

d) It allows you to make new friends while learning a foreign language. New and interesting people really strive to develop lifelong friendships, worthwhile goals and learning another language will speed up the process. Language expresses our feelings, our desires; helps to reach out and connect with other people around us and forms meaningful relationships.

e) Learning a foreign language encourages you to think more openly. Learning a foreign language and immersion in an entirely new culture and worldview - open-minded, is the surest way to become an understanding, tolerant person, and that's for sure priceless. Seeing the world from a different perspective and where you and others are understanding that you have arrived is a fantastic, eye-opening experience.

f) Learning foreign languages helps to better understand their language and culture. Learning a foreign language can involve you in reverse psychology and allows you to better understand your language and culture by comparison. This is one of the most unexpected benefits of learning a foreign language.

Conclusion

To conclude, the importance of language is that it can be used efficiently as a vehicle for our thoughts. The individual who has been subjected to a specific language from birth is most probably in the habit of thinking in that language.

The proficiency helps in an undisturbed thought-flow process that can prove a godsend in both personal and professional life. Remember it is the thoughts that take shape and are expressed as words, ideas and gestures later on. Without the thoughts, you will not be able to find a medium for expressing yourself. The importance of language was that with time it became the means of expression amongst human beings. Remember language opens the minds of people and makes them aware of their surroundings. It acts as a guiding force that helps to develop minds, perceptions and of course personality. The importance of language is that it makes it possible to have a meaningful conversation with a person. It helps to gather the facts without assumptions so that a person can understand the actual information and arrive at a decision. Another importance of language is that it helps to convey the emotions, feelings or gathered facts to someone else in a precise manner. It is the language that provides an individual with the ability to convey or transmit ideas effectively about lots of things. It has become easy to express, understand, identify, convey and interpret various states of emotion.

All in all, language is always open-ended to welcome the new cultural experiences. It modifies itself to suit the new demands of the situation. At the same time language is extendable to give

expression to new cultural expression. It is the culture that makes the language. Whereas, language in its turn reflects culture, preserves it and passes it on to the next generation. Both culture and language are the inseparable aspects of the social behavior; throw more light on each other, mold and shape enriching each other.

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